

FELLOWSHIP

April 2025

Re-imagining Srinagar City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighbourhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship, and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

Nāgrika does not independently verify all the facts or statements in this document and does not assume responsibility for any errors, inaccuracies, or inconsistencies. The use of Nāgrika’s branding denotes the document’s origin within a guided fellowship process, not an endorsement of specific content. The document has been formatted by Nāgrika for presentation consistency; no edits have been made to the fellow’s original content.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance and cultural context of their cities.. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and develop thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is a emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Re-imagining Srinagar

I often think, what if our cities could talk to us just once? What would they say? Would they tell us about the different times they have witnessed or the degradation and threat they are witnessing? Would they celebrate their people, or would they question them? With that in mind, I began exploring Srinagar to gather different perspectives. Obviously, cities wouldn't talk. But we could.

Maybe Srinagar would whisper to us, Do you remember who I am? I am you, and you are me. We both reflect the unique charm. A charm of lush green gardens where flowers bloom and of lanes that hum the song of life. Or if we were to ask the same thing to a figure from the past, what would he or she say? I wondered.

Remembering Mehjoor, a Kashmiri poet, he would call upon us :

Vwolo has baagvaano navbahaaruk shaan paadaa kar
Phwolan gul gath karan bulbul tithee saamaan paadaa kar
Come, gardener! Create the glory of spring! Make guls bloom and bulbuls sing – create such haunts!

Chaman varaan rivaan shabnam tsätith jaamay
Pareshan gul
Gulan tay bulbullan andar dubaaray jaan paadaa kar
The dew weeps and your garden lies desolate;
Tearing their robes, your flowers are distracted;
Breathe life once again into the lifeless gul and the bulbul!

Everyday Life

The call to prayers from mosques and chants from temples wake Srinagar up. The cold water of the Jhelum makes it fresh. The lotuses of Dal Lake add the freshness to the air.

Ghulam Muhammad is a 78-year-old baker. His ideal day starts in the traditional kandur dukan (bakery shop) very early in the morning, almost in darkness, to make fresh Kashmiri bread. He makes different kinds of bread depending on the strength of heat in the open clay ovens throughout the day. In Srinagar, most people start their day with traditional noon chai (salt tea) and the bread that bakers like Ghulam Muhammad bake. Such traditional bakery points are common across neighborhoods and people discuss their activities and opinions in these small shops. Though these bakers spend most of their day in their shops with continual opportunities to produce loaves of bread and rest.

Most people are either working or studying. And they follow the same monotonous routine for around six days a week. Burhan, a 21-year-old boy, said, “ My ideal day starts with a walk around Joggers Park (close to Rajbagh) in Srinagar. Around this area, we have some good green spaces. Then I spend the rest of the day in college.” These community spaces are also evening relaxation spaces for most people. The issue regarding these community spaces is their uneven distribution. Thus, most neighborhoods don't have such spaces in their proximity. While the city does provide a few options in these spaces, such as parks, libraries, and reading rooms, there is a lack of variety.

Suppose a young child wants to learn archery in Srinagar; he or she would have almost no options. Moreover, schools in the city also fail to provide such opportunities.

“In our schools, too, we don't have many activities apart from studying. There are no clubs and other extracurriculars in most of our schools,” said Pakeeza.

Homemakers like Nowsheeba's mother's routine get affected by the electricity issues of the city, providing no escape from the monotonous routine. It also affects the study and routines of countless students who are studying in the city, like Nowsheeba.

Irfan Attari is a manager of an NGO. His ideal day involves meeting like-minded individuals and contributing to social work. “There is a lack of volunteering in the community... We must focus on awareness related to social work,” said Irfan. “Religious places like mosques, temples, gurudwaras, and churches can integrate such community programs,” added Pakeeza.

“The riverside of Jhelum has been recently developed as a Smart City project where people can now relax,” said Rahila. Srinagar has tried to develop the nightlife in the city.

Figure 1
Source: Rahila Bilal

Figure 2
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-Rahila, Srinagar

Places of Belonging

I asked the residents what one word they would use to describe Srinagar. Almost all of them used the word “beautiful.” One can easily feel the attachment that locals have for the city. “Downtown Srinagar is my favorite place... It is pretty much filled with commercial establishments, and the old architecture is in shambles. In the race of modernization, we have continuously lost our cultural essence. Renovating old buildings and promoting local goods would help for sure. Our scenic beauty, like Dal Lake, Pari Mahal, and Mughal gardens, is a recluse from our usual life, and their maintenance would make the experience even better,” added Baseerat Zargar, a postgraduate student. The clock tower in the city has been recently renovated and has garnered attention to the area, creating nostalgia for many residents and developing a sense of belonging in a new generation. The Badshah tomb, an unusual five-domed structure that dates back to the 15th century, is not being maintained properly and hasn't been repaired for about 35 years.

This testament to the city's architectural excellence in the urban sprawl craves the attention that it and other protected monuments in Srinagar deserve.

Figure 3
Source: Author

People hold their identity and culture dear. Many wish for others to experience the richness of Kashmiri literature and the Sufi traditions of Srinagar. Locals feel that there is a growing need to educate others about the city's culture. Burzahom is an important archaeological site located at Burzahom village in Srinagar district. “But not many people are aware of it,” commented Sheeraz Ahmad while talking about its significance. “We shouldn’t forget our roots,” added a senior citizen.

Rahila, a 2nd-year biochemistry student, shared that her favorite place is Zero Bridge at Rajbagh. It provides her with an escape from her daily schedule. A lot of changes have happened at this place. New eateries have been added and a high influx of tourists can be observed. She is worried about the damage to the place, as she feels it is not properly looked after. I asked her about the places she would recommend to the people in Srinagar, and she answered, “People do not know about museums and what the art and culture department in the city offers. Lots of literacy events, exhibitions, and cultural events take place in the city. The old city of Srinagar can help understand the influence of local culture and can offer a window to look to the past of the city.

Figure 4
Source: Author

Voices of Concern

Unemployment & Drug Abuse

The city where skillful hands carve intricate works now struggles to find new opportunities. From weaving pashmina to the digital age, the employment landscape has been shifting. "Unemployment is driving our youth to the void," said Ghulam Muhammad. The youth of the city are constantly worried about their future. The young graduates are forced to take other small jobs to make ends meet. What is the major cause of this? I asked. "There are no great opportunities in the private sector here," added Rahila.

The state has recorded the highest unemployment rates in recent years, especially in urban areas. "Jobs in Kashmir are scarce because the government sector is the only option, and even there, opportunities are minimal. This forces people to consider jobs like driving an e-rickshaw or running a stall," says Faisal Ahmad, an unemployed graduate. When Greater Kashmir, a newspaper, asked a senior official the same question, he said, "J&K's heavy dependence on government sector employment has been a significant impediment to job creation. The private sector has not developed at the same pace as in other regions."

The impact of unemployment extends much further. It fuels migration, mental health issues, and substance abuse. Many young people leave Srinagar in hopes of a better future. A lack of awareness and skill-based training limits their potential. This has created a situation of confusion, hopelessness, and constant stress. Drug abuse concerns the residents on a deeper level and is a degradation to the city. The majority of drug abusers are in the 26-35 age group. Cannabis and heroin are the most common substances abused. Youth support is needed in the city.

Without proper intervention, we may lose Srinagar to despair.

The Fading Craft

Kashmiri walnut woodwork is famous around the world and is considered the finest. Srinagar is the hub of such master craftsmen. From shawl making to papier-maché, the centuries-old craft is the identity of the city. These master residents have kept their heritage alive. When I asked such a craftsman where he drew his inspiration from, he said, “Srinagar... We draw inspiration from the plants, animals, old architecture, chinars, roses, and mountains of Srinagar.” If they don't keep these great crafts alive, then the future won't be good.

Walnut wood carving craft is succumbing to its slow death. Locals feel that there is no financial benefit in the work, and youngsters feel they won't be able to reach the level of senior mastermen. The quality of the material has also suffered, and there is, sadly, no replacement for the masters. Mr. Rasheed is one such craftsman. He stressed the importance of preserving the heritage of the city. He commented, “Srinagar doesn't have dedicated art schools where such traditional skills would be pursued. Moreover, machine-made goods and cheap quality are the competitors. Youngsters don't see a future in it, and there is no support for artisans on a great level.”

Figure 5
Artwork Credit: Aisha Basharat

Environmental concerns

“I have seen Jhelum drying up literally. It has become so shallow. There is no such sewage system, and new developmental projects around the river have caused damage and eutrophication of the river,” said Rahila. Locals observe unregulated construction, improper waste disposal systems, and emissions from vehicles as contributing factors. Srinagar is dynamic and continually changing. Many water bodies and streams are filled with garbage and waste. The city holds countless water bodies in itself.

Neighborhoods and communities close to these resources are dependent on them for food and fodder. Residents watching the wetlands like Hokersar welcome migratory species has become a popular activity. It engages them in fruitful discussion as they document these species. But over time, the pure water channels have turned into dry, muddy stretches. There has been a significant reduction in the original size of such water bodies. Heavy siltation, encroachment, and unsustainable practices have caused almost half of the lakes and wetlands of Srinagar to become lost, and we might not be able to recover them ever, alas! . The following pictures clicked by Rahila describe the state of Jhelum.

Irfan Attari is a manager of an NGO. His ideal day involves meeting like-minded individuals and contributing to social work. “There is a lack of volunteering in the community... We must focus on awareness related to social work,” said Irfan. “ Religious places like mosques, temples, gurudwaras, and churches can integrate such community programs,” added Pakeeza.

Figure 6
Source: Rahila Bilal

Figure 7
Source: Rahila Bilal

Environmental concerns

“The riverside of Jhelum has been recently developed as a Smart City project where people can now relax”, said Rahila. Srinagar has tried to develop the nightlife in the city.

“Garbage is everywhere on these streets”, commented a senior citizen Fatima. Poor urban planning acts as a precursor to such problems. This is a contributing factor of the canine crisis in the city. The open dumping sites in different areas in the city continue to be breeding sites for stray dogs and different infections.

"Srinagar's deteriorating air quality, particularly during winter months, was identified as a critical factor in the rising disease burden. Srinagar continues to be one of the most polluted cities, even in winter, particularly in winter," Dr. Iqbal, Former Head of Cardiology SKIMS, told Greater Kashmir.

Aisha, a school student, shared that every day there is some or other construction going on in the city. “ However, there are no barriers to the construction dust. Whenever we used to pass from the area in the school van, we used to hold our breath”.

Figure 8: Clogged drains and plastic waste thrown in them
Source: Author

Dreams for Tomorrow

City and Citizens

Small cities may have a lot of issues and problems. However, it is its citizens that shape it. Policy makers, IAS officers, social workers, and local entrepreneurs are continuously inspiring the college-going youth. Individuals like Rahila Bilal aim to work on the restoration of Jhelum and create employability in the future. When I asked citizens of distinctive backgrounds what Srinagar would look like in 10 years, they were full of aspirations, dreams, hopes, and some fears. Hopes about a positive future and fears about losing this beautiful city's charm were quite evident.

Burhan, a 21-year-old, told me that we, the residents of this city, need better infrastructure and urban planning, sustainable tourism, and better policies that prioritize the environment and people. He said, “If there is one project that I would implement in the city, it would be providing a better educational platform to young children and working on lost traditions and reviving some forgotten aspects of our city.”

After working in many organizations in Srinagar, Mir Aftab started “Thrive Kashmir,” an NGO that organizes various medical camps, donation events, and major health-specific events and provides wheelchairs and oxygen concentrators to the needy. He said to me, “We have made a small database of blood donors so that if anyone needs blood, we’ll be on the front frontline”. When I asked him about who inspires him in Srinagar, he said, “My personal moral sense and my team members, the majority of them are younger than me (students).”

Figure 9
Source: Irfan Attari

Figure 10
Source: Irfan Attari Kashmiri Press

Sheraz Ahmad, who is a treasurer at an organization and a law student from Kashmir University, is passionate about providing opportunities to the youth and eradicating the stigma against the law by providing necessary awareness to the residents, which is crucial as the involvement of residents in policies is the only way residents could live their dreams of today and hopes of tomorrow .

Irfan Attari is a manager of an NGO called “Foundation for Youth Web.” He has organized the first TEDx in Polo Ground, Srinagar. His work mainly focuses on women's empowerment, cybersecurity, the environment, and skill development in the city. “We align talented youth with different ministries (like MSME) to get loans to start their own businesses.” He also works closely with them to streamline their projects well. His project “Drug Free Kashmir” works specifically for drug abuse in Srinagar, where his organization’s motto is “ Reach the youth before dealers do.”

City and Change

Innovation is key in changing the fate of Srinagar. Recently, I noticed indigenous trees (Chinars) getting ‘Digital Tree Aadhars’ in Srinagar. This geotagged, QR-enabled innovative solution by the Jammu and Kashmir Forest Research Institute aims to protect this important part of the heritage of the city. By leveraging such technological solutions, the department aims to preserve species that are significant to the city.

The majority of the Smart City projects in Srinagar are completed. The city has witnessed redevelopment of Lal Chowk, upgrades to MA Road and Residency Road, riverfront modification, the Integrated Traffic Management System (ITMS), the SD Net, and the Srinagar data network (Intranet). The upcoming milestone projects include improvements to Batmaloo, Mominabad Road, Dalgate-Gojwara Road, and others.

Conclusion

Maybe Srinagar would whisper to us,
“Do you remember who I am?”
“Yes, we remember, and we care” would be the answer of the
residents of Srinagar.

Srinagar is at a crossroads where we have a choice to make. The residents here share a collective vision to transform Srinagar in a way that it can offer every comfort that a city can offer while being cherished by nature. A regular employee after finishing his daily work should be able to relax in a clean, green space. Homemakers should be able to break their monotonous routine via various activities that their community club might offer. Students should have access to learning facilities. In conclusion, locals here want Srinagar to be the city of growth, opportunity, and development, not merely the city of survival. Let's continue to work for this reimagined Srinagar.

*Maybe Srinagar would whisper to us,
“Do you remember who I am?”*

*“Yes, we remember, and we care” would be
the answer of the residents of Srinagar.*

-Author

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Fellowship was partly supported by :

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Umar Shareef, from Jammu and Kashmir, is a Biotechnology student with a passion for research, writing, and creating positive change. Combining his academic focus with six years of community service, he has worked to improve literacy and numeracy rates in underserved communities. Umar enjoys reading, writing, and painting, which provide him with creative and reflective outlets. Known for his eloquence in public speaking and his dedication to making a difference, he seeks every opportunity to grow. Aspiring to make impactful contributions in biotechnology, he is committed to advancing both science and society on a global scale.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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